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АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ДИНАМИКИ ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТИ И СМЕРТНОСТИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ В СВЯЗИ С РАКОМ МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ

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Аннотация: Изучена динамика показателей заболеваемости, инвалидности и смертности населения Республики Беларусь раком молочной железы за период 1986–2019 гг. установлен рост данного заболевания у населения Республики Беларусь в постчернобыльский период. В 2017 г. уровень заболеваемости населения был в 2,5 раза выше по сравнению с 1989 г. Количество пациентов с впервые в жизни установленным диагнозом рак молочной железы в 2019 гг. 1,3 раза выше по сравнению с 2010. Выявлено смещение возрастного пика заболеваемости раком молочной железы женского населения с 57-61 год на 65-69 лет за данный период.

Ключевые слова: рак молочной железы, заболеваемость, инвалидность, смертность

THE ANALYSIS OF THE MODERN DYNAMICS OF INCIDENCE AND MORTALITY OF THE POPULATION OF REPUBLIC OF BELARUS DUE TO THE BREAST CANCER

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Annotation: Dynamics of indexes of incidence, disability and mortality of the population of Republic of Belarus by a breast cancer during 1986-2019 is studied body height of this disease at the population of Republic of Belarus during the post-Chernobyl period. In 2017 the incidence of the population was 2,5 times higher in comparison with 1989. The number of patients with for the first time in life the established diagnosis a breast cancer in 2019 1,3 times are higher in comparison with 2010. Shift of age peak of cancer cases of a mammary gland of female population about 57-61 for 65-69 years for this period is revealed.

Keywords: breast cancer, incidence, disability, mortality

Relevance. The breast cancer is one of the oncopathologies, which are most extended on a global scale and the first place on mortality takes the second place in structure of oncological diseases of female population in the world. Annually more than 1,38 million new cases of a breast cancer come to light and about 500,000 women in connection with this pathology die, cases at men make less than 1 % [1].

The breast cancer takes the second place in structure of oncological incidence at female population in Republic of Belarus (17,6 %) and the first place in structure of mortality of women from malignant new growths (16,9 %) [2, 3].

It is possible to assume that a part of the registered increase in incidence of a breast cancer at the population of Republic of Belarus during the post-Chernobyl period of time can be bound both to radiation exposure as a result of the Chernobyl accident, and as a result of action of the complex of factors of accident including created against the background of the steady psychoemotional stress at the considerable proportion of affected population of a syndrome of a chronic adaptation overvoltage [4, 5].

Research objective. Studying of dynamics of indexes of incidence, disability and mortality of the population of Republic of Belarus of a breast cancer during 1986-2019.

Materials and research techniques. In work were used: comparative and estimated, analytical and epidemiological research techniques. Served as materials for a research given the state statistical reporting and the Ministry of Health of Republic of Belarus.

Results and their discussion. When studying an epidemiological situation in Republic of Belarus it is established that in 1989-2002 mean value of an index of cancer cases of a mammary gland made 46,5 on 100 thousand of

the population (from 35,4 in 1989 up to 57,5 cases on 100 thousand of the population in 2002). The highest level of malignant new growths of a mammary gland was registered in 1989-2002 in the Gomel region (57,3 cases on 100 thousand of the population). Also authentically, more high levels of cancer cases of a mammary gland were noted across Minsk (50,5 on 100 thousand of the population) and the Vitebsk region (49,6 on 100 thousand of the population). The index of primary incidence of this pathology was maximum in age group 57-61 years. For 2002-2011 the indicator of cancer cases of a mammary gland increased by 1,33 times (from 57,5 in 2002 to 76,7 cases by 100 thousand of the population in 2011) [6, 7].

The indicator of cancer cases of a mammary gland during 2011-2017 averaged 82,25 cases on 100 thousand of the population (from 76,7 in 2011 up to 87,8 cases on 100 thousand of the population in 2017). The number of patients for the first time in life the established diagnosis averaged a breast cancer of 2010-2019 46,4 on 100 thousand of the population (from 40,3 in 2010 up to 52,5 cases on 100 thousand of the population in 2019)

It should be noted that during the period from 1977 to 1994 increase in frequency of cancer cases of a mammary gland by 1,5 times took place in Gomel and by 1,9 times – in Mogilev areas. At the same time, it is important to emphasize that the datum level of an index of incidence in the Gomel region in 1977 made 20,0, and in Mogilev – 16,7. In the analysis of oncological pathology on areas and Minsk the highest rate of cancer cases of a mammary gland in 2011-2017 is established at residents of Minsk (69,2 on 100 thousand of the population) and the population of the Vitebsk region (63,2 on 100 thousand of the population). The least indicator – is noted in the Brest and Grodno regions (44,1 and 42,7 on 100 thousand of the population respectively). It is also necessary to note the shift of a maximum of incidence of this pathology from age group in 60-64 years (in 2002-2006 and 2006-2010) for 65-69 years (in 2011-2015).

It is established that the cancer cases of a mammary gland are higher at city women in comparison with rural (by 1,2-1,4 times). The incidence of this pathology grew by 1,8 times at city women (from 50,5 by 100 thousand of the population in 1995 up to 88,4 on 100 thousand of the population in 2017) and at female residents of the village twice (from 36,7 on 100 thousand of the population in 1995 up to 73,7 on 100 thousand of the population in 2017) [8] that demonstrates more considerable growth rate of incidence at country people in comparison with city.

When studying distribution of incidence on an age existence of idiosyncrasies is revealed. Body height of this pathology began from 25-29

years and continued up to 60-64 years, and each next year of life increased risk of a disease approximately by 5 cases on 100 thousand women. Further, with age the incidence gradually decreased. The peak of cancer cases of a mammary gland is established in age group of 65-69 years.

Long-term dynamics of mortality from a breast cancer for 2001-2014 was characterized by the unidirectional moderate tendency to decrease. Rate of decrease was 2,06 %. The indicator of mortality of women from a breast cancer in Belarus during 2001 for 2017 decreased on 3,5 by 100 thousand of the population. In 2019 mortality increased by 1,09 % in comparison with 2018 (12,1 cases on 100 thousand of the population in 2018 and 13,2 cases on 100 thousand of the population in 2019). It is established that mortality in 2019 was higher at urban population (13,3 on 100 thousand of the population) in comparison with rural by 1,2 times (10,9 on 100 thousand of the population). It is also necessary to note increase by 1,08 times of mortality of urban population during the period since 2018-2019 (from 12,3 on 100 thousand of the population in 2018 up to 13,3 on 100 thousand of the population in 2019) and decrease of mortality of country people during the same period by 1,02 times (from 11,1 on 100 thousand of the population in 2018 and 10,9 on 100 thousand of the population in 2019).

In the analysis of mortality from this oncological pathology on areas and Minsk the highest rate in 2018-2019 is noted among residents of the Vitebsk region (15,7 on 100 thousand of the population in 2018 and 13,5 on 100 thousand of the population in 2019), Minsk (12,5 on 100 thousand of the population in 2018 and 14,0 on 100 thousand of the population in 2019), the Gomel region (12,2 on 100 thousand of the population in 2018 and 14,6 on 100 thousand of the population in 2019). For 2018-2019 the index of mortality from a breast cancer decreased in the Minsk region by 1,13 times (from 12,7 by 100 thousand of the population in 2018 and 11,2 on 100 thousand of the population in 2019). In other areas increase in an index of mortality from this pathology is noted.

Conclusions. Thus, as a result of the research conducted by us body height of this disease at the population of Republic of Belarus during the post-Chernobyl period is established that can demonstrate, on the one hand, decrease in level of health and protective forces of an organism, and, on the other hand, improvement of quality of diagnosis of this pathology. In 2017 the incidence of the population was 2,5 times higher in comparison with 1989. The number of patients with for the first time in life the established diagnosis a breast cancer in 2019 1,3 times are higher in comparison with 2010. Shift of

age peak of cancer cases of a mammary gland of female population about 57-61 for 65-69 years for this period is revealed.

Aggravation of risks of this disease on the one hand in the conditions of ecologically destabilized environment is established what confirms high levels of incidence in the Gomel region and Minsk, and on the other hand larger abundance a breast cancer at city dwellers in comparison with rural.

When studying statistical data increase in an index of mortality during 2018–2019 was revealed. The greatest indexes are established in the Vitebsk, Minsk regions that testifies to the insufficient level of detection of a breast cancer at early stages, and in the conditions of ecologically destabilized environment in Minsk.

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